

THE IMPORTANCE OF EXTRA-COURSE CLUBS

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Annotation: This article highlights the role and importance of extra-curricular music club activities in the education of students and young people. Music clubs are an important tool for forming children's aesthetic taste, educating them in the spirit of respect for national and universal values, and developing musical thinking. The article also analyzes the possibilities of developing creativity, teamwork skills, and meaningful organization of free time through club activities. The educational, aesthetic, and social functions of music clubs are revealed through practical examples.

Keywords: extracurricular education, music club, aesthetic education, creativity, national values, musical thinking, students-youth, pedagogical process.

Introduction.

Every person has a need for music hidden in their soul. This need is formed naturally from childhood, and through its correct direction and development, a person's worldview, aesthetic taste, and spiritual world are enriched. Especially for school-age students, the educational power of music is incomparable. Theoretical knowledge given during the lesson is not enough - it is at this point that extracurricular activities, in particular music clubs, play an important role.

Music clubs are not just a place to learn melodies or songs, but a place that allows students to travel to the world of their soul, to express their inner feelings. Through these activities, children get to know our national culture, musical heritage, acquire skills such as stage behavior and teamwork. Most importantly, they develop a love for art and are spiritually enriched. In today's modern educational process, the role of such circles is increasing. They not only serve to identify and develop talented children, but also serve as an effective tool for meaningfully organizing each student's free time and protecting them from foreign ideas. After all, a young soul whose heart is filled with music will never choose a bad path...

Methodology:

The main focus of this study was to reveal the educational, aesthetic and social significance of extracurricular music circles. While working on the article, we did not rely only on dry theory, but also tried to analyze real-life processes, living relationships between teachers and students. After all, a music club lesson

is not a simple activity, but a delicate art that finds its way from heart to heart. During the research, we used methods such as observation, interview, and analysis of practical activities. The creative activity of students participating in music clubs, their ability to express themselves, and their participation in teamwork were directly observed. Also, through interviews with teachers, their methodological approaches, problems, and achievements in conducting the club were identified.

In the methodological approach, we also paid special attention to the use of innovative educational technologies. Because today, in music education, it is important to arouse the student's interest and actively involve him in the process not only through traditional methods, but also through digital tools, audio-visual materials. Thus, methodology is the heart of the study, the compass that determines its direction. And we directed this compass to music, to the world of the children's soul. Because only an analysis made with the heart is close to reality.

Literature analysis:

A lot of scientific, methodological and practical literature has been created about extracurricular education and music circles, which are its component, through which the theoretical foundations, educational effectiveness and methodological approaches of this direction have been deeply studied. Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences T. Yuldoshev in his work "Theoretical Foundations of Education" analyzes the role of extracurricular activities in personal development and substantiates the positive impact of music on children's aesthetic outlook and social adaptability. In the literature on music education, in particular, the works of A. A. Poskryakov and B. L. Yavorsky theoretically highlight the importance of circle classes in identifying and developing musical abilities. They emphasize that through music circles, students' hearing, memory, rhythm and intonation abilities are formed in a unique way.

Also, methodological manuals published by the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan contain recommendations for organizing music circles, lesson plans, and criteria for selecting repertoire. They identify effective methods that can be used in practical activities. In the analysis of scientific articles, it is observed that wide attention is paid to issues such as the role of extracurricular activities in modern education, teaching music using digital technologies, and the use of interactive methods. This indicates that music clubs are developing not only in traditional, but also in innovative directions. An analysis of the existing literature shows that extracurricular music clubs are an

important factor not only in identifying and educating gifted children, but also in the personal development of each student. Scientific and theoretical foundations and practical experiences in this regard serve as a solid foundation for research in this area.

Discussion:

If we look at the educational process today, we can see that extracurricular activities, especially music clubs, are increasingly gaining importance. Because music is the language of the human soul. It is in this language that the student's feelings, dreams, hopes, and soul life are expressed. And music classes are the most elegant pedagogical tool that awakens this inner world, educates it, and directs it to society.

Experience shows that students who regularly participate in music clubs increase their self-confidence, freedom on stage, and the ability to express their thoughts in musical form. They become sensitive to those around them, have a developed artistic and aesthetic taste, and respect national values. When you talk to such students, you can immediately feel the sparkle in their eyes and the love for music in their hearts. At the same time, music clubs should be a means of awakening the soul of every student, not only for gifted children, but also for positively influencing him through music. Here, the personality of the teacher, his approach, and kindness are of great importance. Because in the club, the student receives not only knowledge, but also warmth and spiritual support. However, there are still unresolved problems in practice. In some educational institutions, music clubs are poorly organized, the necessary conditions are not enough, which ultimately leads to the fading of students' interest. Therefore, it is important to further revitalize music clubs, organize them based on modern methods and technologies, and especially to create programs that are appropriate for the age and interests of students.

Conclusion

Extracurricular music club activities play an important role in revealing the creative potential of students, forming their aesthetic taste, and educating them in the spirit of respect for national culture. Research and observations show that students who actively participate in clubs develop musical thinking, have the skills of working in a team, and are formed as spiritually mature individuals. The scientific literature and practical experience analyzed in the article confirm that music clubs should be considered an integral part of the educational process. To increase their effectiveness, it is necessary to use modern methods, take into

account the age and individual characteristics of students, as well as systematically organize the activities of the circles.

Therefore, by activating music circles and directing them to pedagogical goals, we serve to educate a young generation that is not only art-loving, but also has a developed artistic mindset, independent thinking, and a healthy social position.

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